

REOMANNISOL: EXPERIENCE OF APPLICATION IN TRAUMATOLOGY

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Summary

The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of the drug "Reomannisol" in patients with injuries of different etiology on the activity of lipid peroxidation (LPO) and the state of antioxidant system (AOS). The study was conducted in the surgical intensive care unit of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Traumatology and Orthopedics (RSSPMCTO). The obtained data show that the investigated preparation has a pronounced antioxidant effect, increases the activity of AOS enzymes, thus stabilizing biomembranes. Application of the preparation "Reomannisol" effectively restored hemodynamic physiological and blood biochemical analysis indices in clinical application in patients with various types of musculoskeletal traumas, in hemorrhagic shock, as well as effectively reduced the intensity of lipid peroxidation processes, increased the activity of antioxidant defense enzymes and by its activity is not inferior to the preparation "Rheosorbilact".

Key words: Reomannisol, LPO, AOS, antioxidant effect.

Аннотация

Целью исследования явилось изучение влияния препарата «Реоманнисол» у пациентов с травмами различной этиологии на активность перекисного окисления липидов (ПОЛ) и состояние антиоксидантной системы (АОС). Исследование было проведено в отделении хирургической реанимации Республиканского специализированного научно-практического медицинского центра травматологии и ортопедии (РСНПМЦТО). Полученные данные показывают, что исследуемый препарат обладает выраженным антиоксидантным эффектом, повышает активность ферментов АОС, стабилизируя, тем самым, биомембраны. Реоманнисол эффективно восстанавливал гемодинамические физиологические и биохимические показатели при клиническом применении у пациентов с различными видами травм опорно-двигательного аппарата, при геморрагическом шоке, а также эффективно снижал интенсивность процессов перекисного окисления липидов, повышал активность ферментов антиоксидантной защиты и по своей активности не уступает реосорбилакту. Реоманнисол, ПОЛ, АОС, антиоксидантный эффект.

In recent years, the problem of treatment of patients in critical and extreme conditions accompanying trauma of various etiologies, especially in the acute period, does not lose its relevance, as the mortality rate according to WHO data in victims reaches 50%. In this connection, all over the world works on the development of new, more effective means of infusion therapy are being carried out, and considerable attention is paid to antioxidant drugs [2]. The Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan developed and studied the preparation "Reomannisol", which includes a natural metabolite of the Krebs cycle - sodium succinate and mannitol, which has antioxidant properties and diuretic effect [1].

Purpose of the study. To study the effect of the preparation "Reomannisol" in patients with injuries of different etiology on the activity of lipid peroxidation (LPO) and the state of antioxidant system (AOS).

Materials and methods of research

The study of the effectiveness of the preparation "Reomannisol" was carried out in the department of surgical resuscitation of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical

Medical Center of Traumatology and Orthopedics (RSSPMCTO). For the study 60 patients with reliably established diagnosis of water-electrolyte balance disorders, craniocerebral trauma, spinal cord injury, fractures of various etiologies, systemic inflammatory response syndrome, fat embolism and shocks of various etiologies, treated in the department of surgical resuscitation of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Traumatology and Orthopedics, were selected.

The results of the study showed that "Reomannisol" effectively restored hemodynamic, physiological and biochemical parameters in clinical application in patients with various types of injuries of the musculoskeletal system. Against the background of treatment with the preparation "Reomannisol" of the patients of the experimental group there were observed shifts expressed in the reduction of pulse rate by 13.6%, which reached the values of normal values, reduction of body temperature and improvement of blood saturation. The dynamics of these clinical parameters indicates that the use of "Reomannisol" against the background of complex intensive therapy, reduces the main manifestations of intoxication of the body, improves tissue perfusion, improves blood hemoglobin saturation with oxygen and its activity is not inferior to "Rheosorbilact".

Infusion of "Rheosorbilact" and «Reomannisol» significantly reduced high MDA levels by 1.2 and 1.5 times ($p < 0.05$), diene ketones by 1.3 and 1.6 times ($p < 0.05$), diene conjugates by 1.2 and 1.6 times ($p < 0.05$), respectively. As the results of the study showed, they were lower when rheomannisol was applied. Apparently, this was due to the activation of AOS enzymes, the activity of which was significantly higher after the application of "Rheomannisol". The activity of catalase increased 1.3 and 1.9 times ($p < 0.05$), SOD 1.9 and 2.6 times ($p < 0.05$), GR 1.5 and 2.3 times ($p < 0.05$), GPO 1.5 and 1.8 times ($p < 0.05$), after application of "Rheosorbilact" and "Reomannisol", respectively. Compared to the effect of "Rheosorbilact", catalase activity was higher by 46.2% ($p < 0.05$), SOD by 70.0% ($p < 0.05$), GR by 80.0% ($p < 0.05$) and GPO by 20.0% ($p < 0.05$) after application of "Reomannisol". Consequently, we can say that the studied preparation has a pronounced antioxidant effect, increases the activity of AOS enzymes, thus stabilizing biomembranes.

In our opinion, such positive effects of the drug "Reomannisol" are related to the fact that this medical preparation contains two antioxidants and is able to improve the energy supply of cells.

Conclusions:

1. The use of the preparation "Reomannisol" in patients with various types of injuries of the musculoskeletal system, in hemorrhagic shock effectively restored their hemodynamic physiological and biochemical parameters. "Reomannisol" by its activity is not inferior to the drug "Rheosorbilact".

2. Blood substitute "Reomannisol" reduces the intensity of lipid peroxidation processes, increases the activity of antioxidant defense enzymes and exceeds the well-known hemocorrector "Rheosorbilact" in its antioxidant properties.

References:

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